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FOODPathS

Co-creating the prototype “Sustainable Food Systems” Partnership – Project Summary

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Rationale

The food sector increasingly is impacted by climate change, land degradation, biodiversity loss, hunger, malnutrition, diet-related diseases, food and packaging waste and safety, scarcity of fresh water and (renewable) resources, ecosystem services, social and economic inequalities, political tensions, and safeguarding food cultural heritage. Considering **today's severe crises**, an accelerated transition to sustainable food systems in Europe is imperative. Therefore, the **EC with the Member States** aims to establish the **'Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) for people, planet and climate'**. This Partnership should be able to confront challenges via co-funded R&I projects and strategies, systemic approaches using case studies in Living Labs, agendas for **Research, Innovation, Policy-science topics and Education (RIPE)** and Policies (Fig. right).

The project aims

FOODPathS' will design the **'Prototype SFS Partnership'** by executing eight inter-connected Work Packages (Fig. left). The Prototype will serve as the first version of *HOW* the future Partnership will function from 2024 onwards. This includes its co-funding strategies, governance model, *Modus Operandi*, sustainability charter, strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), and vitrine with co-creation cases. It will also list potential trade-offs and will propose ways of communicating with other HorizonEurope Partnerships.

Tasks

FOODPathS will develop (a) **food system (FS) concepts** (Fig. right) to understand relationships between food actors ('players'), their food handling activities (*moves*), used products ('pieces'), geographic-socio-cultural contexts ('playing fields'), duration of actions ('time'), (un-) sustainable outcomes ('win/lose'), regulations, ambitions, and R&I co-funding options ('rules'), (b) a **Hub of FS (Living) Labs** to experiment with multi-actor co-creation processes, (c) an FS **Observatory** for monitoring sustainability performance of EU FS, and (d) **RIPE** agendas to select most appropriate focus areas and leverage points.

Systemic Approach

Systemic approaches will be at the core of the future Partnership. Hence, FOODPathS will explore multi-scale and multi-actor approaches that allow adapting strategies based on gathered insights (Fig. left). This will help in **defining EU-wide common priorities** as well as **country-region-community-specific focus points**. Altogether, they will show the **richness of European cases**, infrastructures, networks, data, etc.

